

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

ATMOSPHERIC AIR LEGAL PROTECTION IN THE PRE-WAR ECONOMY OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

Article proposed are presented study's results of the problem of atmospheric air legal protection from negative anthropogenic and economic impact in pre-war Ukraine. The problems at the level of energy, coal and mining industries, as well as metallurgy were researched. Viewpoint on the protection of atmospheric air in the context of the fiscal policy of the state is presented. Attention was paid to international cooperation on the essence of the problem.

The author's recommendations for reforming the regulatory framework in the area under study are given.

Keywords: atmospheric air, legal protection, economic impact, international cooperation, pre-war Ukraine.

The main text.

Introduction. The current status of the atmospheric air protection problem in the conditions of military entrepreneurship undoubtedly leads us to the need of comparative analysis with a similar problem of the pre-war period. In respect to these circumstances, the term of "protection" should be considered as a comprehensive, interdisciplinary measure; therein legal regulation measures have a primary importance. The relevance of the study in this case is evidently, since the problem of coexistence of a healthy environment and economic progress is a key not only for law, but also for the political economy.

At different times, separate issues of atmospheric air pollution were devoted to the study of E. Guida, O. Obushchak, S. Obushchak, K. Mudrik, V. Petrov, O. Sarkisov, V. Rybachek, A. Chugay, E. Gusev, D. Kukuy, O. Ilyin, S. Bogolyubov, I. Kolosov and many others.

With all respect to the scientific heritage of presented and other authors [13, p.107], the problems of pre-war industrial-related air pollution, in the context of a full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation in Ukraine, are given insufficient research attention.

The purpose of these papers is to evaluate the level of atmospheric air legal protection in the context of pre-war economic activities in the fields of energy, metallurgical and mining industry, on the one hand, and fiscal policy, on the other hand, and a review of foreign doctrine in aforesaid field, both: from the viewpoint of peaceful reforms and partially - wartime assistance.

Materials and Methods. Presented survey has done with assistance of formal and compares methods as special and ontology, deduction, analysis ad synthesis as common, which led to obtain a new data and background for discussion and further investigations from contemporary scientific viewpoint. Thereof, research methodology is based on general scientific methods such as analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, analogy and empirical methods - observation, comparison and statistical ones.

Methodological basis of the survey, undoubtedly, is a dialectical method, the introduction of which provides an opportunity to study the object and subject of

research in their gnoseological unity, as well as the nature of medical law development and their impact, as cause and effect.

Results and Discussion. Pehchevski, considering atmospheric pollution as one of the strategic problems of the country's development, pays attention to the fact that in the pre-war period in Ukraine air emissions mainly consisted of nitrogen oxides, carbon dioxide, sulfur dioxide and dust, but there were also high concentrations of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and heavy metals in industrially developed cities [2].

At the same time, author emphasizes that stationary sources of air pollution make up more than 60% emissions. Approximately 90% of them fall on the mining (~ 30%) and processing (~ 20%) industries, as well as power generation (~ 40%). Non-stationary sources are mainly associated with road transport, which accounts for about 35% of atmospheric pollution [14].

The scientist refers to the fact that the key regulatory act designed to protect the quality of atmospheric air in Ukraine is the Law on the Protection of Ambient Air, structure is prescribed quality standards, MPC of emissions from stationary sources, measures to protect atmospheric air, public and private obligations with respect to air quality, air quality monitoring and responsiveness measures. The law correlates with EU Air Quality Directive, but most of the details such as MPC, monitoring provisions and short/long term air quality improvement action plans are subject to regulatory by-laws [11].

In 2018, thermal power plants released 474,598 tons of SO₂, 92,140 tons of nitrogen oxides and 148,047 tons of dust into the atmosphere. The largest air pollutant with sulfur dioxide was the Uglegorskaya TPP (85,561 tons), then the Zaporizhzhya TPP (74,519 tons). Zaporizhzhya TPP also recorded the highest emissions of nitrogen oxides: 23,222 tons, Luhansk TPP - 9,670 tons. Dust emissions from the Pridneprovskaya TPP turned out to be the highest today: 43,712 tons [1].

In 2019, the highest source of SO₂ emissions was the Burshtynskaya TPP (123,519 tons). Zaporizhzhya TPP remained the highest emitter of nitrogen oxides - 21,830 tons, and Kurakhovskaya TPP - 30,244 tons [16].

In respect to these circumstances, Pehchevski, as recommendations for pre-war Ukraine, provides implication to reduce the operating time of factories during peak hours of electricity consumption in order to reduce the level of emissions of thermal power plants; cancellation of government plans for the construction of new thermal power plants; the development of a long-term national concept of carbon-free energy, and so on and so forth [2].

Havrankova et al. constituted that system of environmental supervision in pre-war Ukraine has been repeatedly criticized for a number of reasons: corruption, inefficiency, unmotivation of employees, insufficient funding, outdated material and technical base, lack of uniform electronic logs of natural resources [3, p. 30]. Author emphasizes three key problems of aforesaid system: insufficiency of institutional organization of the environmental control; due to permanent reorganization with subsequent staff reductions, the regional structure of the Specialized Environmental Inspectorate (SEI) was significantly weakened. Communication between SEI, public authorities and local governments is weak and ineffective, there is practically no cooperation between them; SEI does not have any authority to monitor the environment [4;5;7].

As ways to resolve the presented problems, the scientist proposed to develop an electronic system of environmental reporting and monitoring; entitle the power of the SEI in accordance with the EU 2001/331/EC Recommendations; provide a new control entity with the authority to assess the effectiveness of environmental protection measures funded from state and local budgets [10;12;15].

Kolosov I.V. studying the problem of atmospheric air pollution with metallurgical waste, pays attention to the fact that the waste of Nikopol Ferroalloys Plant, JSC. solely is enough to cover every square kilometer of the Ukrainian with a layer of dust weighing approximately 280 tons. In order to prevent such devastating pollution of the environment, author proposes to regulate the requirements for closed storages of metallurgical waste by the type of spent nuclear fuel storages at the regulatory Acts' level [8, p. 227-229].

Kurylo et al. considering the problem of fiscal measures as tools to prevent atmospheric pollution argued that the economic welfare of the state is inevitably reflected on natural resources, increases the influence of the anthropogenic factor on the world around us. Processes of globalization and social transformation have increased priority protecting the environment, striving to achieve a fair balance and ensure sustainable development of the country. For a long time, the economic development of Ukraine was accompanied by unbalanced the use of natural resources, a low level of priority for environmental protection over economic values, which led to a significant environmental problems. Insufficient financing of environmental protection measures led to an increase in the technogenic burden on the environment. Understanding the significance of the rational consumption and production in the country requires the development and implementation

of rational environmental policies and measures to ensure proper environmental governance with adequate funding to do so.

The scientist insists that the tools and mechanisms of the legal, economic, regulatory system, etc. in Ukraine in most cases only partially comply with established approaches and developed standards for environmental activities of EU countries. Domestic legislation on the protection of atmospheric air should be agreed in accordance with EU standards to be implemented in three directions: legislative, regulatory, technological, etc. Taking into account the existing data and issues affecting air quality, Ukraine should timely outline a strategy for the future to ensure clean air for future generations, implement measures to reduce air pollution, which can significantly improve the overall air quality with positive results [9, p. 315,316,323].

Indiana University McKinney School of Law's Professor Catherine Beck was getting ready to teach her Ukrainian law students at Chernivtsi University about US law when she read the headline "Heavy missile strikes by Russian forces on Ukrainian infrastructure." Meaning, once again, Catherine had to check her email before class to see if any of her students would be able to get on Zoom during the next hour. Beck, a Professor of Legal English at Indiana University McKinney School of Law, volunteered her during the Fall 2022 semester to teach an online legal English course to graduate law students in Ukraine. This course was part of a larger collaborative initiative between Ukrainian law schools and the international law school community, an initiative which grew out of relationships formed over the past decade thanks to seeds planted by groups such as the Legal Writing Institute's Global Legal Writing Skills Committee and the Global Legal Skills Conference community. The purpose was to foster cultural exchange, and the result was the Global Legal Skills Virtual Workshop Series, made possible with support from the US Agency for International Development (USAID)'s Justice for All Activity. The workshop's three short webinars, held over the summer of 2022, brought together law faculty from Ukraine, the United States, and the European Union in an exchange of ideas on how to best support Ukrainian law schools, faculty, and students following Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine. The primary needs identified during these sessions included Legal English courses, guest lectures on a range of topics, and support for Ukrainian legal academics to edit and publish their work in English-language law journals. One effective collaboration was between Zaporizhzhia National University and Professor Robin Juni of GW Law, who gave a guest lecture on environmental law. Faculty and students of the Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University and Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University also joined this lecture. "Prof. Juni's lectures inspire [one] to study more deeply progressive practices of environmental law implementation, in particular in the area of atmospheric air protection from pollution," said Associate Professor Oleksii Makarenkov. Professor Tetyana Kolomoets, Dean of the Zaporizhzhia National University Law Faculty, also expressed gratitude to Juni for teaching a course useful to both teachers and

students and noted that Juni's lectures helped re-establish a lecture series with US specialists that had run for many years until Russia's full-scale invasion on February 24, 2022 [6].

Conclusions. The study conducted encourages us to show the following conclusions:

1. The main pollutants of atmospheric air in pre-war Ukraine were enterprises of energy, coal and mining industries, metallurgy. At the same time, the most common pollutants were oxides of sulfur, nitrogen, carbon.

2. To reduce emissions into the atmosphere, we propose to comprehensively diversify and normatively consolidate the predominant use of renewable sources of electricity: solar, wind, etc., as well as establish legislative, including fiscal incentives for the introduction of such sources of electricity instead of traditional ones.

3. Issues of environmental supervision and control require their proper funding, a deployed regional network, the presence of administrative powers to control both the use of funds from environmental funds of state and local budgets, and bringing it in line with the regulatory requirements of the EU and the Council of Europe.

4. Metallurgical enterprises, as one of the largest pollutants of atmospheric air, must be fully equipped with closed storage facilities for production waste. For failure to comply with this requirement, penalties should be introduced, not bind with the tax-free minimum income of citizens or the minimum wage, but focused on the declared income of the enterprise in the calendar period preceding the violation. In our viewpoint, such sanctions should be from 10 to 50% of the total gross income of the enterprise, depending on the scale of potential pollution. Otherwise, a negligible amount of fines will lead to the profitability of their payment in comparison with the fulfillment of the requirements of environmental protection legislation.

5. At the international level, cooperation with USAID-like programs should be encouraged to improve the level of communication on atmospheric air protection and international standards in aforesaid area.

6. At the legislative level, preferences for environmental-oriented investment over exclusively mercantile should be consolidated in order to achieve a fair balance between rational environmental use and effective economic development of Ukraine.

However, the assessment of the harm caused to atmospheric air by the military actions of the Russian Federation and the methods of jurisdictional compensation for losses caused should be devoted to subsequent scientific research and author's investigations.

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